

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15806992

Consumers' Education And Brand Protection As A Predictor Of Continuous Patronage Of Public Senior Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The researcher explored Consumers' Education and Brand Protection as a Predictor of Continuous Patronage of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. Two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses informed the study. Correlational research design was used in the study and the population comprised 60,581 S.S.3 students from the three hundred and thirty (330) public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The population of 382 participants consisted of SS3 student of public senior secondary schools of Rivers State determined through the stratified random sampling method, and data for the study were obtained from them. Data were gathered through two standardized scales ie 'Consumers' Education Brand Protection Scales' (CEBPS) and 'Continuous Patronage Scale' (CPS). The tools were developed with the modified 4-point Likert scale and face and content validated. The instrument's reliability was 0.92 by Cronbach's Alpha Statistics. Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS) was used in the research due to which simple regression for question 1-2 was obtained. Additionally, t-test associated with multiple regression were used in testing hypotheses. The result from the study revealed that consumer education predicts continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent while the brand protection among others predict less impactful (48%) continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. It was therefore recommended that schools should implement regular parents-students orientation programmes to enhance awareness of institutional offerings and also develop crisis management protocols to mitigate reputation risks that may affect enrolment.

Keywords: Consumer Education, Brand Protection. Continuous Patronage

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Consumer education as the process of equipping individuals with the information and abilities they require to make empowered and informed consumer decisions, comprehend their rights and obligations, risks and advantages of various goods and services, and effective means of handling their finances, strives to empower individuals to be able to effectively navigate the marketplace and make goal- and value-congruent choices (OECD, 2016). Continued patronage on the part of enlightened consumers is needed for a healthy and competitive market. If consumers are enlightened, they can make better choices that best

meet their desires and needs. This can equate to an increased demand for improved products and services, further stimulating business to innovate and improve their products. In addition, informed customers are able to impose responsibility more effectively on businesses to encourage sustainable and ethical operations, initiating constructive change within the market.

Consumer Education and Continuous Patronage of the School System

Consumer education ought to be part of the curriculum within any school system. Students ought to be taught information and skills that will enable them to make sound consumer choices. Consumers within a school system ought to be instructed to make better purchasing decisions and avoid health and financial injuries. Consumer education is seen to succeed in promoting students' awareness of consumer rights and duties (Makela & Peters, 2004; McGregor, 2010; Danilare & Marzano, 2014) and avoiding conspicuous consumption (Unay, 2012). Students who are informed about it by schools through consumer education are capable of influencing their parents' buying decisions (Ekstrom, 2007). This is because consumer education gives students the skill to critically analyse marketing messages, identifying the effect of their (consumers') decisions and how to manage their finances accordingly.

And additionally, a meta-review of school-based financial literacy research found that it had a positive effect on various aspects of financial behaviour like saving, budgeting, and general financial well-being (Fernandes et al., 2014).

Consumer education within the school system may take numerous forms such as systematic class teaching, practice sessions and simulations of life. It may include a very broad range of subjects such as the interpretation of advertisements and traps in marketing, reading and interpreting labels and guarantees on products, personal finance and budgeting, and interpreting consumer rights and protection under law. Through incorporating social responsibility, sustainable consumerism and ethical consumerism issues within the curriculum, schools can educate children to be critical of the effects of their consumption behaviour on the environment, society, and world economy. It can ultimately assist in developing a responsible generation of consumers who are aware of the bigger picture consequences of their consumption behaviour (Boggan, Wicliffe & Moser, 2016).

Ongoing support of the school system is also important in making sure that consumer education is current and timely. The consumer products and services environment changes constantly with new products, technologies and methods that advertise emerging every day. It is thus important for schools to update and modify their consumer education programs regularly to keep up with these advances. This can be done through continued teacher professional development, engagement with consumer and business organizations regular review and updating of the curriculum to make it applicable and representative. If schools can endow pupils with the knowledge and skills they need to become wise, ethical consumers, they can provide them with the capacity to make responsible decisions that are ethical and sustainable throughout their lives.

This can, in turn, contribute to the development of a stronger and more empowered consumer base and assist in the health and vitality of the market overall. By investing in consumer education and putting it at the forefront, we can assist in making sure that future generations are well enough prepared to handle the sophisticated arena of consumer goods and services (National Endowment for Financial Education, 2018).

Brand Protection and Continuous Patronage

Brand protection refers to the strategies and activities aimed at safeguarding a company's brand and reputation from counterfeit products, intellectual property infringement, unauthorized distribution and other threats that can damage the brand's equity and consumer trust. Educational brand protection refers to the efforts made by educational institutions to safeguard their reputation, image and intellectual property in the face of various threats and challenges. Just like any other industry, educational institutions have a brand value or reputation that needs to be protected from risks such as plagiarism, unauthorized use of trademarks and negative publicity (Durkee, 2017). One crucial aspect of educational brand protection is the protection of intellectual property including academic research, proprietary teaching materials and trademarks associated with the institution.

Another important aspect of brand protection in education involves protecting the institution's reputation and image. Negative publicity, scandals or controversies can significantly damage an educational institution's brand and affect its ability to attract students, faculty and funding. Therefore, institutions need to have crisis management strategies to address and mitigate any threats to their reputation. This may involve implementing measures to ensure transparency, accountability and ethical conduct within the institution.

1.2 Statement of Problem

According to Igbudu and Nwadike(2024) quality academic delivery in Nigeria is dependent on the type of leadership style, educational resources, policy evaluation and implementation adopted by the administrators or managers of educational institutions.

The public secondary in the past have experienced bitter experiences whereby the students, parents and even teachers give testimonies of failures such as lack of proper education, illumination and appreciation for consumers of the school system, low school brand and quality, lack of school communication, negative social climate and perception of the public schools etc, that have caused some of the students to be withdrawn by their parents or guardian from the schools, which has caused a reduction in the population of the schools. It is indicated that there is decreased patronage and admission in the public schools due to the fact that, individuals prefer admitting their children in private schools. This issue the researcher is sure, could be caused by the manner in which the school consumers being the customers of the school are treated by the principal that lead individuals not to go and patronize public schools anymore.

Apparently during the late 20th century, suddenly public secondary school enrolments plummeted. This is irrefutable proof of the fact that parents and society in general are quite clearly not only unhappy with the management, quality and product of these public secondary schools but also with the way "they" the customers who visit the public schools regularly are treated and managed. Most of them opt for substitutes such as private schools or home schooling for his/her children or ward, leading to lower patronage and enrolments for the public schools. Majorities who still patronize the aforementioned public schools are either above poverty or above unfairness because most people take their children to better private schools. The researcher is thus interested in the issue of decreased patronage of public secondary schools and aims to determine the degree to which consumer education and brand protection would predict sustained patronage of consumers of public secondary schools in Rivers State.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the objectives of this study are:

- 1) To determine the extent to which consumer education predicts continuous patronage of public secondary schools in Rivers State.
- 2) To establish the extent to which brand protection predicts continuous patronage of public secondary schools in Rivers State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study.

- 1) To what extent does consumer education predict continuous patronage of public secondary schools in Rivers State?
- 2) To what extent does brand protection predict continuous patronage of public secondary schools in Rivers State?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were provided for the study:

- 1) There is no significant prediction of consumer education on continuous patronage of public secondary schools in Rivers State.
- 2) There is no significant prediction of brand protection on continuous patronage of public secondary schools in Rivers State.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The design of the study was correlational research designs. The population for the study comprised 330 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. These schools have a total of 60,581 SS3 students, who were the participants in the study (Rivers State School Management Board, 2024). The sample of the study comprised 397 SS3 students, drawn from a total population of 60,581 students selected using the Taro Yamane and stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for the study was self-developed attitude scale titled the Consumers Education Brand Protection Scale (CEBPS) and the Continuous Patronage Scale (CPS). The Consumers Education Brand Protection Scale (CEBPS) was developed to gather data on school systems consumers’ educational strategies of school principals, while the Continuous Patronage Scale was used to gather data on the patronage of public secondary school systems. The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach's Alpha Statistics. Simple regression was used to answer research questions while. T-test associated with multiple regression were used in testing hypotheses.

4.0 RESULT

4.1 Data Presentation

Research Question 1: *To what extent does consumer education predict continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 4.1: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent to which Consumer Education Predict Continuous Patronage of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	R	Adjusted Square	R Adjusted Square	R Decision
1	.800	.640	.639	High Extent

- 0.00 - 25.00 Very Low Extent
- 26.00 – 50.00 Low Extent
- 51.00 - 75.00 High Extent
- 76.00 – 100.00 Very High Extent

Data on Table 4.1 present the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent to which consumer education predicts continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The regression score came out as 0.800, the regression square as 0.640 and the adjusted regression square as .639 while the coefficient of determination stood at 64%. When reference is made to the scale of measurement, 64% being the coefficient of determination falls between 51.00 - 75.00 (high extent), this shows that consumer education predicts continuous patronage of public secondary schools to a high extent. Based on the foregoing, the researcher ascertained that, consumer education predicts continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools to a high extent (64%)

Research Question 2: *To what extent does brand protection predict continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 4.1.2: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on the extent to which Brand Protection Predict Continuous Patronage of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Decision
1	.698	.488	.486	Low Extent

*The scale of measurement for Table 4.2 applies

Data on Table 4.1.2 present the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent to which brand protection predict continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The regression score came out as 0.698, the regression square as 0.488 and adjusted regression square as 0.486 while the coefficient of determination stood at 48.6%. When reference is made to the scale of measurement, 48.6% being the coefficient of determination falls between 26.00 – 50.00 (low extent), showing that, brand

protection predict continuous patronage of public secondary schools in Rivers State to a low extent. Based on foregoing, the researcher ascertained that, brand protection predict continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a low extent (48.6%)

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant prediction of consumer education on continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4.2.1: Summary t-test Associated with Simple Regression Analysis on the Prediction of Consumer Education on Continuous Patronage of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model		Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.698	.116		6.016	.001
	Consumer Education	.780	.030	.800	25.972	.001

Data on Table 4.2.1 show the summary of t-test associated with simple regression on the prediction of consumer education on continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. With the respondents as 382, the t-test calculated value used in testing the hypothesis resulted in 25.972 using 381 degree of freedom at 0.05 alpha level of significance and significant value of 0.001. At a significant value of 0.001 and 0.05 alpha level of significance, 0.001 is less than the alpha significant value of 0.05. Based on these observations, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis that there is no significant prediction of consumer education on continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and confirmed that there is a significant prediction of consumer education on continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant prediction of brand protection on continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4.2.2: Summary of t-test Associated with Simple Regression Analysis on the Prediction of Brand Protection on Continuous Patronage of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model		Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.843	.147		5.731	.001
	Brand Protection	.719	.038	.698	19.021	.001

Data on Table 4.2.2 show the summary of t-test associated with simple regression on the prediction of brand protection on continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. With the respondents as 382, the t-test calculated value used in testing the hypothesis resulted in 19.021 using 381 degree of freedom at 0.05 alpha level of significance and significant value of 0.001. At a significant value of 0.001 and 0.05 alpha level of significance, the null hypotheses was rejected because the significant value of 0.001 is less than the alpha significant value of 0.05. Based on these observations, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis that there is no significant prediction of brand protection on continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and confirmed that there is a significant prediction of brand protection on continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

4.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS/IMPLICATIONS

Extent Which Consumer Education Predict Continuous Patronage of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

The findings revealed that consumer education significantly predicts continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent. The regression analysis yielded a strong positive relationship, with a regression coefficient of 0.800 and a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 64%, indicating that consumer education accounts for a substantial portion of the variance in school patronage. The adjusted R^2 value of 0.639 further confirms the robustness of this relationship, minimizing the likelihood of overestimation. According to the scale of measurement, a 64% predictive power falls within the high extent range (51.00–75.00), underscoring the influential role of consumer education in shaping parents' and students' decisions to remain enrolled in public senior secondary schools.

These results affirm the view of Ubah (2019) that improving consumer education initiatives such as awareness campaigns, transparency in school operations, and effective communication of educational benefits could enhance trust and loyalty among stakeholders.

Extent Which Brand Protection Predict Continuous Patronage of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

The findings indicate that brand protection has a limited, yet notable, influence on continuous patronage of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The regression analysis yielded a coefficient of 0.698, with an R^2 value of 0.488, suggesting that brand protection accounts for 48.6% of the variance in sustained school enrolment. While the adjusted R^2 of 0.486 confirms the model's consistency, the predictive power falls within the 'low extent' range (26.00–50.00) on the measurement scale. This implies that while brand protection such as safeguarding a school's reputation, maintaining quality standards, and preventing negative publicity contributes to patronage, its impact is not as strong as other factor (consumer education). Schools with stronger brand protection mechanisms may still see some retention benefits, but this factor alone is insufficient to guarantee long-term enrolment stability.

The moderate influence of brand protection supports the findings of Johnson (2019) that public secondary schools should not rely solely on reputation management to sustain patronage but should integrate it with more impactful strategies, such as improving service quality and stakeholder engagement. These findings highlight the need for a balanced approach where brand protection complements rather than dominates efforts to enhance public senior secondary schools patronage in Rivers State.

5.1 CONCLUSION

The findings of this study provide robust empirical evidence that consumer education demonstrate strong predictive power with continuous patronage of public secondary schools in Rivers State.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proffered:

- 1) Consumer Education: Schools should implement regular parent-student orientation programmes to enhance awareness of institutional offerings, as consumer education significantly predicts patronage (64%).
- 2) Brand Protection: While this variable is less impactful (48.6%), schools should still develop crisis management protocols to mitigate reputation risks that may affect enrolment.

REFERENCES

- Adebayo, S. O. & Olaore, F. A. (2019). The effect of consumer management on continuous patronage of public secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 33(5), 722-736.
- Adekunle, O. (2019). Evaluating the impact of consumer appreciation on school patronage in the public education sector. *International Journal of Research*, 8(2), 120-135.

- Adeyemi, T. (2018). Consumer management in school systems and its impact on continuous patronage. *Journal of Educational Management*, 6(2), 45-58.
- Adeyemi, T., Ocho, L. & Ogundokun, A. (2018). The role of consumer satisfaction in secondary education: strategies for school management. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 5(4), 112-126.
- Akinyode, B.F. & Olaitan, O.O. (2019). Impact of activities on public secondary school in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 6 (11), 15-26.
- Alao, E. M. (2018). Communication and its effects on students' patronage of public secondary schools. Unpublished Master's thesis, University of Lagos.
- Anderson, M. (2016). Perceived quality of education and patronage of public secondary schools. Doctoral dissertation, University of Port Harcourt Repository.
- Ani, C. (2017). Consumer satisfaction and loyalty in public secondary schools. *Journal of Educational Research*, 29(3), 215-229.
- Appietu, M.E & Mensah, C. (2020). Examining boarding school foodservice satisfaction and patronage of sources of meals. *Journal of Culinary Science & Technology* 18 (6), 507-526.
- Beltramini, R. F., Peterson, R. A., & Kozmetsky, G. (1982). Concerns of college students regarding business ethics. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 1(3), 231-244.
- Brown, K. (2018). The role of customer satisfaction in brand loyalty towards public secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 32(4), 654-670.
- Bush, T. & Bell, L. (Ed.). (2002). *the principles and practice of educational management*. Paul Chapman Publishing.
- Boggan, S. Wicliffe, N. & Moser, M. (2016). Consumer education in schools: a forgotten curriculum in the Consumer World. *Journal of Business and Education Leadership*, 6(1), 23-32.
- Education Week (2021). The state of education in 2021. The state of education in 2021. <https://www.edweek.org/leadership/the-state-of-education-2021/2021>.
- Fernandes, D., Lynch Jr, J. G., & Netemeyer, R. G. (2014). Financial literacy, financial education and downstream financial behaviors. *Management Science*, 60(8), 1861-1883.
- Flanigan, G. & Krockover, T. (2017). School principal's role in engaging school system consumers. *Journal of School Leadership*, 27(4), 538-561.
- Garcia, M., & Smith, K. (2021). The impact of parent involvement on educational outcomes: A Longitudinal Study. *Journal of School and Family Partnerships*, 8(1), 45-60.
- Garg, A. & Rahman, Z. (2013). Consumer-brand relationship quality: a synthesis and future research agenda. *Journal of Brand Management*, 20(5), 647-663.
- Igbudu, Jennifer Nnenda, (2025). Effective Resource Utilization in Revitalising Educational Productivity in Nigeria: Challenges and Strategies. *International Journal of Educational Management*, Rivers State University., 1(2), 339-351. <https://ijedm.com/index.php/ijedm/article/view/64>
- Igbudu, J.N, & Nwadike S.I (2024). Application of Posdcorb plus EA in Education for quality academic delivery in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academia*, Volume 7 No. 1, February, 2024
- Lusardi, A., & Mitchell, O. S. (2008). Planning and financial literacy: How do women fare? *American Economic Review*, 98(2), 413-417.
- Oliver, R. L. (1999). Whence consumer loyalty? *Journal of Marketing*, 63(Special Issue), 33-44.
- Oliver, R. L. (2010). *Satisfaction: A behavioral perspective on the consumer*. Routledge.
- Ubah, C. (2019). Consumer education and the performance of public secondary schools in Rivers State. *Journal of Consumer Studies*, 14(2), 200-215.